

Naphthoxyacetylacetophenone as a Selective Reagent for Determination of Iron

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A new spectrophotometric method for microdetermination of iron using naphthoxyacetylacetophenone (NAA) is reported. The complex is formed instantaneously in cold at pH 5.5 and can be extracted in toluene. It shows maximum absorbance at 390 nm. Beer's law is valid over the range of 0.5 to 8.0 $\mu\text{g Fe ml}^{-1}$. The complex is stable and sensitivity of determination is 0.008 $\mu\text{g Fe cm}^{-2}$. Many common ions are tolerated to a large extent. The method is simple, rapid, selective and can be used satisfactorily for the determination of iron in drug and ore.

SEVERAL reagents have been proposed for the spectrophotometric determination of iron^{1,2}. The metal is known to be present in small amounts in various synthetic and natural objects and investigations are mainly centered in suggesting new methods for its estimation in trace quantity in such objects. In a previous communication from this laboratory, photometric determination of iron in drugs and ore has been reported³. Recently various photometric methods have been reported for its estimation in spring water, drugs, serum, paper, alloys and graphite⁴⁻⁹.

In the present work a new diketone, naphthoxyacetylacetophenone has been studied as an analytical reagent for iron. The reagent forms yellowish-red complex with Fe^{2+} as well as Fe^{3+} . The colour development is instantaneous and there is negligible interference from other transition metals commonly associated with iron. The complex has relatively high molar absorptivity as compared to picolinaldehyde, 4-phenyl-3-thiosemicarbazone¹⁰, 2,4,6-trihydroxyacetophenone¹¹, 8-quinolinol-sodium dodecyl sulphate¹² and 2,4-dihydroxydibenzoic acid¹³ complexes of iron. Sensitivity of determination (0.008 $\mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$), is far better than that of 3-phenyl-5-isoazolin-4-carboxylic acid¹⁴, 2,4-dihydroxyvalerophenone¹⁵ and isonitrosobenzoylacetone-pyridine¹⁶.

Experimental

A Beckman DU-2 spectrophotometer with quartz cuvettes of 1 cm thickness was used for spectrophotometric measurements.

A stock $1.0 \times 10^{-2} M$ solution of Fe^{2+} was prepared by dissolving a known weight of ferrous ammonium sulphate (A.R.) in double-distilled water acidified with 2-3 drops of HCl. Working solution containing 25 $\mu\text{g Fe ml}^{-1}$ was

prepared by suitable dilution of stock solution. Fresh solutions were always used.

Acetate buffer of pH 5.5 was prepared by mixing 1 M solution of sodium acetate and acetic acid in appropriate ratio.

The reagent NAA was prepared from naphthoxyacetic acid. The acid itself was prepared by the reaction of β -naphthol and chloroacetic acid in NaOH¹⁷. The ethyl ester of naphthoxyacetic acid (3.6 g) and acetophenone (3.0 g) were taken in a round bottom flask. To it 30 ml of potassium tertiary butoxide (1 g potassium in 30 ml tertiary butanol) were added. The mixture was stirred for 1 h under inert, anhydrous condition until pink coloured precipitate was obtained. The excess of tertiary butanol was removed by vacuum distillation and crude naphthoxyacetylacetophenone was recrystallised from ethanol (6.2 g), m.p. 109-110°.

General procedure: Aliquot of solution containing 5-80 μg of iron was taken in a beaker. To it 10 ml of acetate buffer of pH 5.5 was added and the total volume was made to 20 ml with distilled water. To it was then added 5 ml of $1.47 \times 10^{-5} M$ solution of NAA in alcohol. The yellowish orange Fe-NAA complex formed was extracted by equilibrating for 30 sec with 10 ml toluene. The organic layer was separated and its absorbance was noted at 390 nm against a reagent blank prepared in an identical manner. The concentration of iron in an unknown solution was calculated with the help of a calibration curve.

Results and Discussion

Optimum conditions: The complexation reaction is instantaneous after mixing both the solutions and takes place in cold. One extraction with 10 ml of toluene and equilibration period of 30 sec is

sufficient for quantitative extraction of iron. The complex is highly stable, the absorbance remains constant for 8 days. The extraction behaviour of Fe-NAA complex as a function of pH was studied. It was found that extraction was quantitative between pH 5.0 to 6.0. Sodium acetate-acetic acid buffer is most suitable to maintain the pH. Sodium hydrogen phosphate-potassium dihydrogen phosphate and potassium hydrogen phthalate-NaOH buffers are also suitable for quantitative extraction. 5 ml of $1.47 \times 10^{-5} M$ NAA solution in alcohol is necessary for complete reaction. Excess of reagent does not make any significant difference in the absorbance.

Toluene and ethyl acetate quantitatively extract the complex. In other solvents such as carbon tetrachloride, benzene, chloroform and methyl isobutyl ketone, the percent extraction was found to be 94.0, 88.0, 77.0 and 74.0, respectively.

Spectral characteristics † The spectra of Fe-NAA complex is shown in Fig. 1. It shows two maxima, one at 390 nm and another at 450 nm. The λ_{max} at 390 nm is more prominent and hence all measurements were made at 390 nm. Under the conditions, the reagent alone does not show

Fig. 1. Absorption spectra of Fe-NAA system. Fe = 25 μg , pH = 5.5, 5 ml of $1.47 \times 10^{-5} M$ NAA, extraction in 10 ml toluene.

any absorbance against the solvent blank. Both Fe^{2+} and Fe^{3+} react identically with the reagent. The range in which Beer's law is followed and found to be from 0.5 to 8.0 $\mu\text{g Fe ml}^{-1}$. The optimum range of iron determination as evaluated from Ringbom plot is 1.0 to 7.9 $\mu\text{g Fe ml}^{-1}$. Sandell's sensitivity and molar absorptivity are 0.008 $\mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$ and $6.925 \times 10^3 \text{ dm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$, respectively. From 10 different sets of observations the relative standard deviation was found to be 0.66%.

Effect of diverse ions : The effect of the presence of other ions in the analysis of Fe by the above

method was studied. The following amounts (μg) of foreign ions were found to give less than $\pm 2\%$ error in the determination of 25 $\mu\text{g Fe}$. Chloride (18000), iodide (5050), thiocyanate (2350), sulphate (5750), thiosulphate (6700), oxalate (3500), citrate (5600), tartrate (5920), Ag^+ (4000), Mg^{2+} (2500), Mn^{2+} (2000), Co^{2+} (3500), Ni^{2+} (2000), Cu^{2+} (2500), Zn^{2+} (2500), Hg^{2+} (8000), Cd^{2+} (1120), Ca^{2+} (1200), Pd^{2+} (860), Al^{3+} (200), Bi^{3+} (1680), Cr^{3+} (1560), Ga^{3+} (700), Rh^{3+} (825), Ru^{3+} (470), Ir^{3+} (1350), Pt^{4+} (1560), Ti^{4+} (600), Os^{4+} (540), V^{5+} (625), Mo^{6+} (770) and W^{6+} (1475). EDTA interferes strongly in the determination and must be absent.

Analytical applications :

Determination of iron in drugs : Iron present in drugs in the form of ferrous sulphate, ferrous succinate and ferrous fumarate can be conveniently determined by this method. For this, tablets or capsules of known weight containing iron in the form of ferrous sulphate, ferrous succinate were placed in a beaker. To it was added 50 ml of distilled water containing 2-3 ml of concentrated HCl and the mixture was boiled until complete dissolution occurred. The boiling mixture was filtered through a filter paper previously rinsed with distilled water. The residue was washed with 20 ml of boiling distilled water and the final volume of filtrate was made up to 250 ml in a volumetric flask with distilled water. In case of tablet or capsule containing iron as ferrous fumarate, digestion with 20 ml of concentrated H_2SO_4 for 2-3 h in a Kjeldahl's flask was carried out. The solution was transferred to a beaker, concentrated to about 1 ml, cooled and diluted with distilled water. Insoluble matter was removed by filtration and the filtrate was made up to 250 ml in a volumetric flask with distilled water. In case of liquid samples, 2 ml of liquid was diluted with distilled water in a 250 ml volumetric flask containing 2 ml of concentrated HCl. In all cases solution containing 25 $\mu\text{g Fe ml}^{-1}$ was prepared by suitable dilution and the procedure was followed. 10 Tablets/capsules or liquid portions were taken in each case and experiments were performed 5 times. In every case, the result obtained was compared with the standard o-phenanthroline method for iron estimation^{1,2}. The results obtained are given in Table 1.

Determination of iron in ore : The ore sample was obtained from Indian Bureau of Mines, Nagpur. About 0.4 g sample was weighed accurately and dissolved in a mixture of concentrated HCl and HNO_3 (15+10 ml). The solution was heated till all the nitrous fumes were removed. 20 ml of 1 : 1 H_2SO_4 was added and the solution was evaporated almost to dryness. 50 ml of distilled water was added and the residue was digested till all the salts dissolved. It was cooled and filtered through a filter paper. The working solution ($\sim 25 \mu\text{g Fe ml}^{-1}$) was prepared by appropriate dilution of this

TABLE 1—DETERMINATION OF IRON IN DRUGS

Name of drug	Iron present as	Iron** present mg	Iron found mg	Error %
Iberol	Ferrous sulphate	105.0	104.6	0.38
Fersolate	Ferrous sulphate	39.12	38.52	1.53
Compoferon	Ferrous sulphate	110.20	109.05	1.03
Fesofar	Ferrous sulphate	55.10	55.10	0.00
Exifol	Ferrous sulphate	55.10	54.12	1.23
Hematrine	Ferrous succinate	32.49	32.27	0.67
Becadexamine	Ferrous fumarate	16.43	16.43	0.00
Macrafolin	Ferrous fumarate	65.46	64.67	1.65
Iberol*	Ferrous sulphate	5.25	5.25	0.00
Fercina*	Ferroglycine sulphate	5.00	5.00	0.00

* Liquids. ** *O*-Phenanthroline method.

solution. 1 ml of this solution was taken and the procedure was followed. The experiments were performed with 10 different portions of solutions and results were compared with a standard *o*-phenanthroline method^{1,2}.

The percentage of iron was found to be 26.04 which is in agreement with a standard *o*-phenanthroline method.

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